

A Survey on the Employment Status of GEP Graduates of NIPSC

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ABSTRACT: This descriptive study aimed to track the employment status of GEP graduates of NIPSC through the use of a tracer study form from the office of the Vice President for Academic Affairs of the College. The data were analysed using frequency counts and percentages. The study revealed that the GEP graduates were all employed, their status of employment were all permanent, they were receiving a monthly salary of Php20, 000 and above and their current jobs were related to their field of specialization regardless of program, sex, and age. Furthermore, 50% of the graduates of MAT program were supervisors, 8% were school heads, and 42% were classroom teachers. In the MAEd program, 34% were supervisors, 38% were school heads, and 28% were classroom teachers. As to the Ed.D program, 40% were supervisors, 50% were school heads and only 1% comprised the classroom teaching. The result suggests that the completion of their MAT, MAED, and EdD degree had been a great help to the graduates. It became an instrument for them to get promoted, to gain greater confidence, and feel secured of their tenure as teachers.

KEYWORDS: employment status, GEP graduates, degree program, sex, age

I. INTRODUCTION

An elemental identification of a successful Graduate Education Program (GEP) is the thriving employment rate of its alumni. Data and information on the employment status of the GEP graduates are important tier to an educational institution in bettering its curricula thus providing a more comprehensive and suitable education to its present and future learners.

Peng-Tan and Nang (2012) suggests that the success of an institution lies in its graduates and the quality of graduates is measured through the employability and transformation they gained as they exposed themselves to the real world. Furthermore Peng-Tan and Nang (2012) averred that tracing graduates is an important action on the part of the institution, making it an essential tool in the evaluation of institution's program for improvement. Flomo (2013) on the other hand noted that tracing graduates is a retrospective assessment of the graduates' course in relation to the industry's needs and the connection between the theory learned at school and the application of the same to work.

This study was based on the employability model. The concept draws a line between employment and employability. Being employed means having a job and being employable means having the qualities needed to maintain employment and progress at work place (de Guzman and de Costa, 2008 in Bolaane et al., 2010, Herrnstein et al., 2012). The importance of graduate education through employability of graduates was based on the characteristics that have impact on the quality of program to the world of work (Storen & Aamodt, 2010). Educational systems shape the matching of people to jobs. To match people to job, they should have acquired knowledge and skills that are required by employers.

This is also anchored on the human capital theory of Schultz and Beber in Cantina (2018) which states that the economic prosperity and functioning of the nation depends on its physical human stock. In this theory human capital represents the investment of the people that could enhance their economic productivity. This theory presents further a positive picture of higher education portraying it as provider of skills needed in performing complex jobs making people more productive and thus sustaining economic growth.

The Graduate Education program of Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College (NIPSC) has already gone a long way. Thus, a follow up study is needed to determine the employment status and/or work performance of its graduates. Monitoring graduates and former students provide one form of outcome measurements that can be used to address issues of accountability, program review, community relations, as well as marketing. This survey is a groundwork in transcending limitations and restrictions that currently externalizes in the actuality of the academe. This consequential study persevered to outline the resulting performance of the GEP graduates in achieving a better status in the work sector. As much as the school recognizes personal development, it is also essential that the graduates can grow and find their place in the community.

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Hence, this study was conducted to determine the employment status of the GEP graduates of NIPSC, Estancia, Iloilo from 2010-2020. Specifically, this study aimed to know the employment status of the GEP graduates, their monthly income, and if their present position is related to their field of specialization when they are grouped according to degree program, sex, and age.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive survey method of research which concerns itself with the present phenomena in terms of conditions, practices beliefs, processes, relationships or trends invariably (Salaria, 2012). Hence this study is descriptive because it tried to determine the employability status of the GEP graduates of NIPSC. This tracer study is a method intended to locate and track down the graduates in order to seek and develop feedback from their alma mater. Also, it is geared to generate or influence decision-making and planning with regard to the development of the curricula.

B. Respondents of the Study

The respondents were the graduates of the Graduate Education Program for the last ten years on the following degree programs: Doctor of Education (major in Educational Management), Master of Arts in Education (majors in Educational Management and Mathematics), and Master of Arts in Teaching (majors in English, Mathematics, and Science). The respondents were taken from the list of graduate students of the GEP and all of them were considered and were given the Tracer Study Form. However, due to the pandemic, there were only almost 50% that were retrieved and considered for this study.

C. Research Instrument

The researchers utilized the Tracer Study Form from the Office of the Vice President for Academic Affairs of the College which consists of Part I, the Personal Profile of the Respondents, Part II, Employment Profile, Part III, Employment Record, and Part IV, Proof of Employment.

D. Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers distributed the instrument personally and through online due to the location of the respondents. Due to the pandemic, only almost 50% were retrieved since there has been lockdowns of some areas, no and/or low connectivity problems, and Work from Home scheme of some respondents. Some respondents from far flung and island barangays were not reached and instruments were not retrieved.

Only the retrieved instruments were considered and were tallied, analysed and interpreted to determine results.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Employment Status of GEP Graduates by Degree Program, Sex, and Age

Table 1 shows the employment status of GEP graduates as to program, sex, and age.

Result revealed that graduates of MAT (100%), MAEd (100%) and Ed.D (100%) programs were all employed regardless of sex and age. It shows that for a Master's or Doctoral degree holder, there is a big opportunity to be employed since most companies or institutions believed that they have sufficient academic skills. According to Mihail and Kloutsiniotis (2014) a graduate degree (MBA) seems to be of considerable value for two-thirds of the graduates in finding employment and nearly 40% responded that MBA contributed to a large extent in their hiring process. The evaluation was based on a 5-point Likert scale in which responses ranged from 3-4, specifically MBA contributes to finding a job after graduation (3.74).

The graduates of MAT (100%), MAEd (100%) and Ed.D (100%) programs were all permanent regardless of sex and age. This result is expected considering that majority of the respondents are above 35 years old, which can be assumed that they are already in service for a long time and with their MAT, MA Ed., or Ed.D degree they can perform competently. Hence, they are all permanently employed. This result is contradictory to the study of Segismundo and Zacarias (2017) in MAEd program where 93.4% were permanent or regular and 6.6% were contractual. Likewise to the study of Cagasan et al. (2017) which reveals that 83.6% of the respondents were regular or permanent, 6.8% were contractual, 4.1% were temporary, 2.7% were casual, 1.4% were self-employed and 1.4% were not employed.

Table 1. Employment Status of GEP Graduates by Degree Program, Sex, and Age

Degree Program	Sex	Age	Employment		TOTAL
			Employed (f)	Not Employed (f)	
MAT	Male	35 and below	1	0	1
		above 35	4	0	4
	Female	35 and below	4	0	4
		above 35	15	0	15
Percentage			100%	0%	100%

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MAEd	Male	35 and below	4	0	4
		above 35	5	0	5
	Female	35 and below	9	0	9
		above 35	11	0	11
Percentage			100%	0%	100%
Ed.D	Male	35 and below	1	0	1
		above 35	1	0	1
	Female	35 and below	2	0	2
		above 35	6	0	6
Percentage			100%	0%	100%

Degree Program	Sex	Age	Employment Status		TOTAL
			Permanent (f)	Non-permanent (f)	
MAT	Male	35 and below	1	0	1
		above 35	4	0	4
	Female	35 and below	4	0	4
		above 35	15	0	15
Percentage			100%	0%	100%
MAEd	Male	35 and below	4	0	4
		above 35	5	0	5
	Female	35 and below	9	0	9
		above 35	11	0	11
Percentage			100%	0%	100%
Ed.D	Male	35 and below	1	0	1
		above 35	1	0	1
	Female	35 and below	2	0	2
		above 35	6	0	6
Percentage			100%	0%	100%

B. Monthly Income of GEP Graduates by Degree Program, Sex, and Age

Table 2 shows the monthly income of graduates as to degree program, sex, and age.

Results revealed that graduates of MAT (100%), MAEd (100%) and Ed.D (100%) programs had monthly income of 20,000 pesos and above regardless of sex and age. This result may not only be contributed to salary standardization particularly to those employed in the government, but it follows that after the respondents had graduated in MAT, MAEd, or Ed.D they were promoted. In congruence to their promotion is the increase in salary.

This result contradicts with the study of Segismundo and Zacarias (2017) which reveals that 8% of the graduates receive highest compensation bracket of P51,000 and above; 2% receive from P41,000 to P50,000; 31% from P31,000 to P40,000; 42% from P21,000 to P30,000 and 18% receive from P20,000 and below. It also contradicts with Cagasan et al. which reveals that almost half of the respondents had a monthly salary ranging from P21,000 to P30,000 (26%) and from P11,000 to P20,000 (21.9%). Only one had an income below P10,000, the others had an income ranging from P31,000 to P90,000.

Table 2: Monthly Income of GEP Graduates by Degree Program, Sex, and Age

Degree Program	Sex	Age	Monthly Income		TOTAL
			Below 20,000 (f)	20,000 and above (f)	
MAT	Male	35 and below	0	1	1
		above 35	0	4	4

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	Female	35 and below	0	4	4
		above 35	0	15	15
Percentage			0%	100%	100%
MAEd	Male	35 and below	0	4	4
		above 35	0	5	5
	Female	35 and below	0	9	9
		above 35	0	11	11
Percentage			0%	100%	100%
Ed.D	Male	35 and below	0	1	1
		above 35	0	1	1
	Female	35 and below	0	2	2
		above 35	0	6	6
Percentage			0%	100%	100%

C. Relatedness of the Present Position of GEP Graduates to Their Field of Specialization when Grouped as to Degree Program, Sex, and Age

Table 3 shows if the present position of the GEP graduates is related to their field of specialization when they were grouped as to degree program, sex, and age.

Result revealed that the present position of the GEP graduates when grouped as to degree program, sex and age was that 50% of the graduates of MAT program were supervisors, 8% were school heads, and 42% were classroom teachers. In the MAEd program, 34% were supervisors, 38% were school heads, and 28% were classroom teachers. As to the Ed.D program, 40% were supervisors, 50% were school heads and only 1% comprised the classroom teaching. This signifies that post graduate education provides a greater chance of promotion in the academe as discussed by Neiworth and Schmieder-Ramirez (2014) in which according to them approximately 81% of the alumni surveyed indicated that attaining an Ed.D degree helped them change their employment status and 71% indicated that the Ed.D program prepared them either “extremely well” or “very well” for their new professional roles. It is also similar to Bueno (2017) which reveals that 53.85% of the Ed.D graduates are occupying key position in the educational institutions as supervisor or head teacher, 42.3% are school principals and 3.85% are Master Teachers. Among the MAEd 65.8% are classroom or Master Teachers, 28.57% head teachers/supervisors, 5.56% are principal. However in the survey of Mihail and Kloutsiniotis (2014) 58% of the respondents replied that a graduate degree (MBA program) had no effect on promotion, whereas 17% indicated that they were promoted once, 11% twice and 14% more than 3 times. Since over half of the sample (58%) responded that they experienced no promotions it can be concluded that there is no clear relationship between MBA degree and the pace of promotion.

The current positions of graduates of MAT (100%), MAEd (100%), and Ed.D (100%) programs were related to their chosen field of specialization regardless of sex and age. This result is an implication that the respondents had no issues of mismatch or underemployment.

This result contradicts to Segismundo and Zacarias (2017) study which reveals that 91% of the MAEd graduates agreed that their jobs are related to their graduate degree while 9% claimed that their current posts are not related in any way to the MAEd degrees they have pursued.

Table 3: Relatedness of the Present Position of GEP Graduates to Their Field of Specialization when Grouped as to Degree Program, Sex, and Age

Degree Program	Sex	Age	Job Relatedness		TOTAL
			Related (f)	Not related (f)	
MAT	Male	35 and below	1	0	1
		above 35	4	0	4
	Female	35 and below	4	0	4
		above 35	15	0	15
Percentage			100%	0%	100%
MAEd	Male	35 and below	4	0	4
		above 35	5	0	5
	Female	35 and below	9	0	9

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		above 35	11	0	11
Percentage			100%	0%	100%
Ed.D	Male	35 and below	1	0	1
		above 35	1	0	1
	Female	35 and below	2	0	2
		above 35	6	0	6
Percentage			100%	0%	100%

Degree Program	Sex	Age	Present Position			TOTAL
			Supervisor (f)	Head (f)	Teacher (f)	
MAT	Male	35 and below	0	0	1	1
		above 35	2	1	1	4
	Female	35 and below	2	0	2	4
		above 35	8	1	6	15
Percentage			50%	8%	42%	100%
MAEd	Male	35 and below	1	3	0	4
		above 35	1	2	2	5
	Female	35 and below	5	3	1	9
		above 35	3	3	5	11
Percentage			34%	38%	28%	100%
Ed.D	Male	35 and below	0	1	0	1
		above 35	1	0	0	1
	Female	35 and below	0	2	0	2
		above 35	3	2	1	6
Percentage			40%	50%	1%	100%

IV. CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded from the result of the study that the GE program of the College was able to help improve the skills of the students and the employment status of the graduates as manifested that they are all permanently employed, promoted to better academic and administrative positions and are receiving high salary. The program is responding to the needs of the industries since the academic acquired skills and competencies of the graduates are relevant to their chosen occupations as evident by the relatedness of their works to their degrees.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Although the results of the study showed that the delivery of the graduate degree program of NIPSC was commendable still it is suggested that a more comprehensive follow-up tracer study (quantitative, qualitative, or correlational) may be conducted, which may include more variables, related to the employability and problems encountered by the graduates and may be suggestions from the graduates to enhance the provision of the graduate degree program of the college can be solicited which can be used as bases to make the graduate curricular offerings of the college more responsive to the needs of the students and the employers.

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